

MAGNETIC FIELD SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF A HIGH-PERMEABILITY SHIELD ON TWISTED PAIR AND COAXIAL CABLES

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ABSTRACT

A braided cable shield has been developed as a possible replacement of electrostatic shields on currently used military cables for low frequency magnetic field below-decks shipboard applications. The purpose of this paper is twofold. First, results of measurements are presented to determine the Effective Loop Area (ELA) of cable samples utilizing a high-permeability braided shield and comparing these results with data for cables constructed to military specifications. Second, results of measurements are presented for determination of the overall shielding effectiveness of a high-permeability braided shield sample and comparing these results with theoretical predicted data.

INTRODUCTION

High-permeability materials have been utilized to shield radiating magnetic fields in submarine and shipboard installations. They reduce the magnetic fields which inductively couple onto interface cabling of sensitive electronic systems, thereby reducing potential electromagnetic interference (EMI). Currently, high-permeability, flexible shielding conduit is the required instrument for resolution of magnetic field susceptibility spatial constraint submarine cabling problems [1]. Since cables must be placed inside the conduit for magnetic field protection, a larger diameter assembly must be accommodated for in the cableway volumes of the ship.

The purpose of this study was to replace the existing electrostatic shields of select Mil-C-17 and Mil-C-915 shipboard cables with a high-permeability, electrostatic combination braided shield, of approximately the same thickness of the current electrostatic shield, and provide comparable shielding effectiveness of magnetic fields to the high-permeability, flexible shielding conduit. If comparable, this technique would facilitate effective shielding without the addition of the high-permeability, shielding conduit, therefore reducing shipboard cableway volumes. Two coaxial cables (RG-214 and RG-264), one triaxial cable (TRF-8), and a shielded twisted pair cable (2SJ-18 equivalent) were tested whose shields were replaced with a 36 AWG Vermalloy® VE622 shield. In addition, a sample of the 36 AWG Vermalloy® VE622 machine braided over a 3/4 inch diameter tube was tested. The Vermalloy® VE622 material is comprised of 80.0% Nickel, 14.9% Iron and 4.2% Molybdenum.

TEST METHODOLOGY

EFFECTIVE LOOP AREA (ELA) OF CABLE SAMPLES

A nine inch diameter Helmholtz coil, with current supplied by a McIntosh Model MI-350 power amplifier, was used to generate the magnetic fields for the high-permeability braided shield cable samples as shown in Figure 1, in accordance with [1]. The frequency and voltage of the input signal were provided by the tracking signal generator section of a HP-3585A spectrum analyzer. The current through the Helmholtz coil was measured with a Pearson Model 411 current transformer whose output was also monitored by the same HP-3585A spectrum analyzer. These test items were located external to a shielded room. A ten foot sample of the test cable was placed into the magnetic field of a calibrated nine inch Helmholtz coil as shown in Figure 1. One end of the cable sample was short-circuited (the cable shield was floated at this end) while the other end of the cable was connected to a second HP-3585A spectrum analyzer, located inside the shielded room (the cable shield was grounded at the shielded room interface). The voltage induced in the cable sample by the magnetic field generated by the Helmholtz coil was measured at the second spectrum analyzer. This spectrum analyzer was located inside a shielded room to ensure isolation of the test sample output. Figure 2 depicts the short-circuiting configurations used for each cable sample. The input current and frequency to the Helmholtz coil, as well as the induced voltage of the tested cable sample were then recorded for nine frequencies ranging from 300 Hz to 100 kHz. Additional investigative data was also recorded for some of the cable samples at 30 Hz, 70 Hz, and 100 Hz.

SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF BRAIDED SHIELD SAMPLE

Shielding effectiveness measurements on a sample of the high permeability shield material, machine braided over a 3/4 inch diameter tube, was obtained for verification of low frequency magnetic field shielding properties of the material. A similar test setup utilizing the nine inch diameter Helmholtz coil, with current supplied by a McIntosh power amplifier, was used for the shielding effectiveness measurements. In addition, a 6 inch long sensing coil, wound on a 3 foot long 1/4 inch diameter fiberglass rod, was individually calibrated at the center of the Helmholtz coil to a known magnetic field. The sensing coil was then inserted inside the braided shield sample and placed into the

Helmholtz coil test system, as depicted in Figure 3. The magnetic field present at the sensing coil, placed inside of the braided shield sample was then recorded on the second HP-3585A spectrum analyzer. The input current and frequency to the

Helmholtz coil, as well as the sensing coil's output voltage, were then recorded for eleven frequencies ranging from 70 Hz to 100 kHz.

FIGURE 1. TEST SETUP FOR MEASURING EFFECTIVE LOOP AREA

FIGURE 2
CABLE CONFIGURATIONS

FIGURE 3. TEST SETUP FOR MEASURING SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS

RESULTS

EFFECTIVE LOOP AREA (ELA) OF CABLE SAMPLES

The induced voltage measurements for each test sample cable were recorded at each of the test frequencies. The ELA of each tested cable sample, Table 1, was then empirically computed from this data using the formula [1]:

$$ELA = \frac{e_{ind}}{0.406 f B}$$

where

- ELA = Effective Loop Area in square inches
- e_{ind} = induced voltage in microvolts
- f = frequency in Hertz
- B = flux density in Gauss

Table 1 also provides a comparison of the ELA of the tested sample cables with the high-permeability braided shield to those without the high-permeability braided shield. The shielding effectiveness of the high-permeability braided shield on the cable samples is defined as the ratio of the ELA of the cable sample without the shield to the ELA of the cable sample with the shield.

SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS OF BRAIDED SHIELD SAMPLE

The shielding effectiveness of the high-permeability braided shield for the testing of the 3/4 inch diameter shield braided over a tube is defined as the ratio of the magnetic field present at the sensing coil external to the braided shield sample to the magnetic field present at the sensing coil internal to the braided shield sample. Table 2 and Figure 4 show the shielding effectiveness results of the high-permeability braided shield material was measured with the magnetic field directed perpendicular to the axis of the cylinder (transverse field).

ANALYSIS

The data compiled in Table 1 shows that for each of the existing military cable samples, except for the RG-214 cable, the replacement of the cable shield with the high-permeability braided shield produces cables that have at a minimum an average ELA ratio of 5 or better, or a calculated shielding effectiveness for these cable assemblies of 14 dB or greater across the frequency range of interest. In the case of the TRF-8 triaxial cable an average ELA ratio of 45 was achieved, or 33 dB.

When the outer shield of the coaxial cable (RG-214) or triaxial cable (between shields TRF-8 case) is used as part of the signal path, the high-permeability braided shield is not effective for shielding against magnetic fields. However, when the high-permeability braided shield is employed as an overall shield

		FREQUENCY (Hz)											AVG	AVG			
		30	70	100	300	700	1,000	3,000	7,000	10,000	30,000	70,000	100,000	RATIO	dB		
TWISTED PAIR	B FIELD (G)	16.79	3.20	3.09	1.00	0.98	1.00	1.00	0.63	0.30	0.06	0.06	0.02	5.02	14.02		
VE3452	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	4.27	1.86	2.88	2.54	5.96	7.85	23.71	35.48	25.41	14.96	29.85	10.96				
W/O SHIELD	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0209	0.0205	0.023	0.0209	0.0214	0.0193	0.0195	0.0198	0.0212	0.0197	0.017	0.0135				
TWISTED PAIR	B FIELD (G)	NR	NR	NR	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	0.63	0.60	0.20				
VE3452 W/	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	NR	NR	NR	0.84	2.11	3.20	9.44	24.55	29.51	38.02	56.89	27.54				
VE622 SHIELD	ELA (sq. in.)	NR	NR	NR	0.0035	0.0037	0.0039	0.0039	0.0043	0.0036	0.0049	0.0034	0.0034				
	ELA RATIO	-	-	-	5.97	5.78	4.95	5.00	4.60	5.89	4.02	5.00	3.97				
	SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS (dB)	-	-	-	15.5	15.2	13.9	14.0	13.3	15.4	12.1	14.0	12.0				
RG-264/A	B FIELD (G)	19.95	18.20	3.16	1.84	0.99	0.97	0.34	0.19	0.20	0.19	0.08	0.04			7.40	17.39
	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	64.57	133.35	33.11	58.21	72.44	103.51	104.71	131.83	184.08	375.84	211.35	109.65				
	ELA (sq. in.)	0.2657	0.2579	0.2579	0.2596	0.2579	0.2639	0.2537	0.2434	0.2299	0.1638	0.0947	0.0752				
V10435-1	B FIELD (G)	19.95	18.20	3.16	1.84	0.99	0.97	0.34	0.19	0.20	0.19	0.08	0.05				
(RG-264/A W/	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	6.61	5.69	3.43	7.85	11.35	16.41	20.18	27.54	37.58	85.11	63.10	51.29				
VE622 SHIELD)	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0272	0.011	0.0267	0.035	0.0404	0.0418	0.0489	0.0509	0.0469	0.0363	0.0273	0.0252				
	ELA RATIO	9.77	23.45	9.66	7.42	6.38	6.31	5.19	4.78	4.90	4.51	3.47	2.98				
	SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS (dB)	19.8	27.4	19.7	17.4	16.1	16.0	14.3	13.6	13.8	13.1	10.8	9.5				
RG-214	B FIELD (G)	16.22	16.41	15.31	6.24	2.60	2.48	0.83	0.35	0.23	0.08	0.03	0.02	0.98	-0.21		
	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	0.89	1.91	1.91	2.24	2.29	2.29	2.26	2.16	2.02	1.29	0.61	0.41				
	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0045	0.0041	0.0031	0.0029	0.0031	0.0023	0.0022	0.0022	0.0022	0.0013	0.0008	0.0006				
VE10435-12	B FIELD (G)	NR	18.20	19.28	2.45	3.55	2.54	1.53	0.67	0.47	0.15	0.06	0.04				
(RG-214 W/	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	NR	0.72	1.12	1.62	4.27	5.07	9.44	7.50	6.10	2.40	1.10	0.89				
VE622 SHIELD)	ELA (sq. in.)	NR	0.0014	0.0014	0.0054	0.0042	0.0049	0.0051	0.0039	0.0032	0.0013	0.0007	0.0006				
	ELA RATIO	-	2.93	2.21	0.54	0.74	0.47	0.43	0.56	0.69	1.00	1.14	1.00				
	SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS (dB)	-	9.3	6.9	-5.4	-2.6	-6.6	-7.3	-5.0	-3.3	0.0	1.2	0.0				
TRF-8	B FIELD (G)	15.14	14.96	21.13	13.96	6.84	4.90	1.68	0.67	0.48	0.16	0.06	0.04			45.28	33.12
coaxial	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	6.53	14.45	29.17	56.23	64.57	66.07	63.10	50.12	40.27	16.41	7.33	5.25				
	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0354	0.034	0.034	0.0331	0.0332	0.0332	0.0309	0.0264	0.0207	0.0084	0.004	0.003				
VE10435-13	B FIELD (G)	NR	NR	NR	13.49	6.17	4.62	1.58	0.68	0.48	0.16	0.06	0.04				
(TRF-8 W/	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	NR	NR	NR	0.44	0.80	1.11	2.04	1.97	1.72	0.65	0.25	0.20				
VE622 SHIELD)	ELA (sq. in.)	NR	NR	NR	0.0003	0.0005	0.0006	0.0011	0.001	0.0009	0.0003	0.0001	0.0001				
	ELA RATIO	-	-	-	110.33	66.40	55.33	28.09	26.40	23.00	28.00	40.00	30.00				
	SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS (dB)	-	-	-	40.9	36.4	34.9	29.0	28.4	27.2	28.9	32.0	29.5				
TRF-8	B FIELD (G)	15.31	14.96	14.13	9.12	4.57	3.31	1.20	0.51	0.35	0.11	0.04	0.03	0.30	-10.45		
between shields	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	5.82	12.74	17.58	33.88	40.74	41.21	40.27	32.36	27.54	14.96	10.47	8.91				
	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0312	0.0299	0.0307	0.0305	0.0314	0.0307	0.0275	0.0225	0.0193	0.0111	0.0093	0.0084				
VE10435-13	B FIELD (G)	10.59	10.12	20.42	13.34	3.39	2.40	0.82	0.35	0.25	0.08	0.03	0.02				
(TRF-8 W/	INDUCED VOLTAGE (uV)	8.32	25.41	82.22	45.19	331.13	266.07	101.16	130.32	130.32	83.18	36.73	21.30				
VE622 SHIELD)	ELA (sq. in.)	0.0645	0.0884	0.0992	0.0278	0.3439	0.2732	0.101	0.1292	0.1308	0.089	0.0486	0.0321				
	ELA RATIO	0.48	0.34	0.31	1.10	0.09	0.11	0.27	0.17	0.15	0.12	0.19	0.26				
	SHIELDING EFFECTIVENESS (dB)	-6.3	-9.4	-10.2	0.8	-20.8	-19.0	-11.3	-15.2	-16.6	-18.1	-14.4	-11.6				

CABLE EFFECTIVE LOOP AREA

TABLE 1

Freq. (Hz)	Magnetic Field at Probe (dBG)		SE (dB)
	w/o shield	w/ shield	
70	-44	-57.5	13.5
100	-44	-57	13
300	-44	-56.9	12.9
700	-44	-56.9	12.9
1000	-44	-56.9	12.9
3000	-44	-56.9	12.9
7000	-44	-56.9	12.9
10000	-44	-56.7	12.7
30000	-44	-56.6	12.6
70000	-44	-56.4	12.4
100000	-44	-56.1	12.1

Shielding Effectiveness (transverse field)

TABLE 2

High-Permeability Braided Shield Sample

Shielding Effectiveness (transverse field)

FIGURE 4

isolated from the signal of the cable (as in the twisted pair, RG-264 and coaxial TRF-8 test case), the maximum magnetic field shielding levels are attained.

Examination of the shielding effectiveness test results of the high-permeability braided shield sample show similar results to the shielded cable sample tests. Table 2 test data shows the braided shield sample's shielding effectiveness as being essentially constant over the frequency range of interest at 13 dB, within the ELA test calculated shielding effectiveness values. Initial pre-test assumptions were that the braided shield sample's shielding effectiveness would be directly proportional to the absorption loss of the braided shield sample material, and therefore the shielding effectiveness should increase exponentially with frequency. In order to further understand why the test data illustrated constant shielding effectiveness over the frequency range of interest, it was decided to evaluate the permeability of the braided shield sample material.

The maximum d.c. permeability of the braided shield material, per the manufacturer's specification sheet, is published as 200,000. The permeability of the braided shield sample was evaluated experimentally over the frequency range of interest. The permeability of the braided shield sample was determined by comparing the inductance measurement of an air core solenoid with the inductance measurement of the solenoid with the braided shield sample as the core. The range of permeability for the braided shield is presented in Table 3 and Figure 5. It is observed from Table 3 that the maximum relative permeability, 88.13, is greatly reduced from the manufacturer's published specification. This reduction in permeability is attributed to the working of the shield material into its present braided form. It is a well known fact that high permeability materials are sensitive to physical stresses (i.e. mechanical shock, machining, etc.) [1]. The permeability, as specified by the manufacturer is that of the material after annealing, were as the relative permeability presented in Figure 5 is that of the material after manufacturing processes where significant physical stress occurs.

Freq. (Hz)	Relative Permeability (min.)	Relative Permeability (max.)
30	33.64	80.73
70	32.57	78.16
100	31.92	76.61
700	36.72	88.13
1000	36.31	87.14
3000	33.28	79.86
7000	30.72	73.72
10000	28.70	68.88
30000	16.42	39.41
70000	3.13	7.51
100000	1.09	2.62

Measured Relative Permeability

TABLE 3

The theoretical shielding effectiveness due entirely to the absorption loss of the braided shield material was then calculated for the high-permeability material using the measured minimum and maximum permeability data of Table 3. The absorption loss (in dB), presented in Table 4 and Figure 6, was calculated as follows:

$$A = 20 \log_{10} e^{\frac{t}{\delta}}$$

where

- A = absorption loss in dB
- t = material thickness in meters
- δ = skin depth in meters

The skin depth, δ, is calculated as follows:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi f \mu \sigma}}$$

where

- f = frequency in Hertz
- μ = permeability of the material in Henries per meter
- σ = conductivity of the material in Siemens per meter

Measured Relative Permeability

FIGURE 5

Freq. (Hz)	Shielding Effic. (min.) (dB)	Shielding Effic. (max.) (dB)
30	4.364057	6.760767
70	6.559119	10.16134
100	7.761613	12.02424
700	22.02481	34.12068
1000	26.1771	40.5534
3000	43.40466	67.24222
7000	63.70063	98.68459
10000	73.5967	114.0155
30000	96.42504	149.381
70000	64.28853	99.59536
100000	45.42619	70.37395

Absorption Loss

TABLE 4

— Minimum absorption loss — Maximum absorption loss

Absorption Loss

FIGURE 6

The theoretical shielding effectiveness data, the absorption loss in dB shown in Figure 6, was not constant with frequency as the Figure 4 shielding effectiveness test data illustrates. Therefore, the changing permeativity of the braided shield material is not responsible for the constant shielding effectiveness response of the braided shield material as shown in Figure 4. It is believed that the apertures in the weave of the high-permeability braided shield sample are responsible for the essentially constant shielding effectiveness with respect to frequency.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study was to replace the existing electrostatic shields of select Mil-C-17 and Mil-C-915 shipboard cables with a high-permeability, electrostatic combination braided shield, of approximately the same thickness of the current electrostatic shield, and provide comparable shielding effectiveness of magnetic fields to the high-permeability, flexible shielding conduit. If comparable, this technique would facilitate effective shielding without the addition of the high-permeability, shielding conduit, therefore reducing shipboard cableway volumes. Based on the tests performed on the cable samples and the tube sample of the high-permeability braided shield, it can be concluded that:

1. The high-permeability braided shield material provides at a minimum 12 dB magnetic field shielding effectiveness essentially constant across the frequency range 70 Hz to 100 kHz.
2. The high-permeability braided shield material, when used as a replacement of electrostatic shielding material in the construction of military cables, will not provide the equivalent magnetic field shielding as the high-permeability, shielding conduit of [1]. However, the use of these shields will reduce the magnetic fields radiating from and to adjacent shipboard cables, and may provide enough shielding in order to eliminate the requirement for conduit.

3. When the outer shield of the coaxial or triaxial cable is used as part of the signal path, the high-permeability braided shield does not provide any improvement for shielding against magnetic fields.

4. For the triaxial cable with the outer shield replaced with the high-permeability braided shield, the shielding effectiveness of this cable was an order of magnitude more than the other cables evaluated in this study, and warrants further investigation.

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